

Estimation of Combining Ability of Maize Inbreds

F M Ali Haydar¹, Saika Kabir Nitu², Uthpal Krishna Roy³, Roni Rani⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department of Botany, University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to assess the combining ability for grain yield and its related components by crossing six diverse maize inbred lines using a half-diallel mating design. A total of 15 F₁ hybrids, along with their six parental lines, were evaluated in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Combining ability analysis indicated that both general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) variances were significant for all studied traits, highlighting the importance of both additive and non-additive gene actions. Grain yield was found to be influenced by both types of gene effects. Most of the crosses exhibited significant and positive SCA effects for several traits, particularly those involving low × average and average × average general combiners. Parent P₄ showed high GCA effects and demonstrated good general combining ability for most traits, except for number of rows per cob and number of grains per row. A comparison of SCA effects with the GCA effects of the respective parents revealed that crosses with high SCA effects for maturity, number of grains per cob, and grain yield per plant generally involved high × low general combiners. The majority of high-yielding crosses with superior SCA effects for grain yield and grains per cob also involved high × low GCA parents. Based on GCA performance, parents P₃ and P₄ were identified as promising genotypes and may be utilized as potential sources in future maize hybridization programs.

Published Online: April 20, 2026

Cite the Article: Ali Haydar, F. M., Nitu, S.K., Roy, U.K., Rani, R. (2026). Estimation of Combining Ability of Maize Inbreds. International Journal of Life Science and Agriculture Research, 5(4), 257-261. <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijlsar/V05I04Y2026-07>

License: This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Corresponding Author:

F M Ali Haydar

INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) plays a vital role in human and livestock nutrition worldwide. It is one of the highest-yielding cereal crops and is valued for its high productivity, low production cost, reduced risk, and multipurpose uses compared with many other crops. The combination of high market demand, relatively low input costs, assured market availability, and high yield potential has generated considerable interest among farmers in maize cultivation. In Bangladesh, maize is gaining increasing popularity, particularly due to its extensive demand in the poultry feed industry (Karim et al., 2018).

Despite the growing demand, Bangladesh relies heavily on imported hybrid maize seeds, which are expensive and often not available to farmers in a timely manner. Maize is the third most important cereal crop in the country after rice and wheat, accounting for approximately 4.8% of the total cropped area and 3.5% of the total value of agricultural output (Ahmad et al., 2011). During the 2014-15 cropping season, maize was cultivated on about 3.25 lakh hectares, producing nearly 22.72 lakh tons of grain (BBS, 2016). The high cost of imported inbred lines and seed supply constraints highlight the urgent need for developing locally adapted, high-yielding, and early-maturing maize hybrids. Farmers would benefit significantly if such hybrids could be produced and distributed domestically.

In this context, the present study was undertaken to evaluate locally developed maize hybrids under Bangladesh conditions and to identify superior inbred lines for hybrid development. Combining ability analysis, specifically general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA), provides valuable information on the breeding potential of inbred lines and their performance in hybrid combinations. Differences in GCA effects are mainly attributed to additive gene action and additive × additive interactions, whereas differences in SCA effects are associated with non-additive genetic variance, including dominance and epistatic interactions (Falconer, 1981). The concepts of GCA and SCA have become increasingly important in plant breeding due to the widespread

adoption of hybrid cultivars across many crops (Wilson et al., 1978).

The evaluation of crosses among inbred lines is a crucial step in the development of superior maize hybrids (Hallauer, 1990). Ideally, this involves the assessment of all possible crosses among selected parents through diallel mating designs, which allow breeders to estimate the genetic potential of individual inbred lines. Diallel analysis provides insights into genetic architecture, including dominance-recessive relationships and other gene interactions. Such analyses have been widely used to study trait inheritance and to identify superior parents for hybrid and cultivar development (Yan and Manjit, 2003).

The primary objectives of combining ability and heterosis studies in plant breeding are to identify elite parental lines, select superior cross combinations, exploit hybrid vigor, and understand the underlying gene action governing yield and its components. General combining ability aids in the identification of superior parents, while specific combining ability facilitates the selection of promising hybrid combinations. Heterosis analysis helps quantify the superiority of F₁ hybrids over their parents and assists in the formation of heterotic groups. Therefore, the present investigation employed a 6 × 6 half-diallel mating design to identify good general combiners and superior cross combinations for the development of suitable maize hybrids under local conditions in Bangladesh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The genetic materials used in this experiment consisted of six maize inbred lines selected from a pool of 25 inbreds, namely IL₄ (P₁), IL₅ (P₂), IL₁₈ (P₃), IL₁₀ (P₄), IL₂₃ (P₅), and IL₁ (P₆). These six parents were crossed in a half-diallel mating design to produce 15 F₁ hybrids: P₁×P₂, P₁×P₃, P₁×P₄, P₁×P₅, P₁×P₆, P₂×P₃, P₂×P₄, P₂×P₅, P₂×P₆, P₃×P₄, P₃×P₅, P₃×P₆, P₄×P₅, P₄×P₆, and P₅×P₆.

Methods

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. Crosses were made in a half-diallel fashion during the 2023-2024 growing season. Plants at the flowering stage, just before anthesis, were selected for controlled pollination.

Collection of Data

Data were recorded from five randomly selected plants from each row for the following traits: days to tasseling (DT), days to silking (DS), number of rows per cob (NRC), number of grains per row (NGR), number of grains per cob (NGC), and grain yield per plant (GYP).

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using standard biometrical techniques of combining ability analysis following Method 1 (parents + F₁s; half-diallel without reciprocals) as described by Griffing (1956). In this study, six parents (n = 6) were involved in the diallel mating system, resulting in 15 F₁s [n(n-1)/2]. Thus, a total of 21 entries comprising six parents and 15 crosses were evaluated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of variance revealed that both general combining ability (GCA) and specific combining ability (SCA) variances were highly significant for all the studied characters (Table 1), indicating the involvement of both additive and non-additive gene actions in the expression of these traits. The ratio of GCA to SCA variances was greater than unity for most of the characters, suggesting that additive gene effects played a more predominant role than non-additive effects. A higher GCA/SCA ratio implies greater predictability of performance based on GCA alone.

The importance of both GCA and SCA variances for grain yield and its contributing traits in maize has also been reported by Moneam et al. (2009) and Karim et al. (2018). In the present study, however, GCA variances were considerably higher than SCA variances for most characters, except for number of rows per cob, indicating the predominance of additive gene action for the inheritance of these traits. Karim et al. (2018) similarly reported higher GCA than SCA variances for days to pollen shedding, plant height, ear height, and grain yield. In contrast, Moneam et al. (2009) and Karim et al. (2018) observed GCA/SCA ratios less than unity for kernels per row, 100-kernel weight, and ear yield per plant, suggesting the predominance of non-additive gene action. The present findings therefore indicate that additive gene effects were more influential for most traits, except number of rows per cob.

Effects of General Combining Ability (GCA): The estimates of GCA effects along with the mean performance of the parents are presented in Table 2. Among the six parents, P₄ emerged as the best general combiner for most of the traits studied, whereas the remaining parents showed good combining ability for specific characters only. A wide range of GCA effects was observed among the parental lines, reflecting substantial genetic variability.

For days to tasseling, days to silking, maturity, number of grains per cob, and grain yield per plant, parents P₁, P₂, and P₄ exhibited significant positive GCA effects along with superior mean performance, indicating that parental mean performance could serve as a useful indicator of combining ability. These parents may therefore be effectively utilized in hybrid breeding programs aimed at improving grain yield and adjusting flowering and maturity duration. Estimates of GCA effects further revealed that parents P₁ and

F M Ali Haydar, et al, Estimation of Combining Ability of Maize Inbreds

P₂ were good general combiners for grain yield, while P₄ and P₅ showed desirable GCA effects for reduced plant stature, suggesting their potential use in breeding for short-statured, high-yielding genotypes.

Overall, parent P₄ was identified as the most promising general combiner for days to tasseling, days to silking, grains per cob, and earliness. Parents P₄ and P₅ also exhibited significant positive GCA effects for ear height, making them suitable donors for improving this trait. Inbreds with good general combining ability for one or more traits can be effectively used as donor parents to accumulate favorable alleles in breeding populations.

Effects of Specific Combining Ability (SCA): The estimates of SCA effects revealed that crosses showing significant positive SCA effects for grain yield generally also exhibited high mean performance, whereas crosses with significant negative SCA effects had lower mean values (Table 3). This relationship indicates the effectiveness of SCA in identifying superior hybrid combinations. The high mean performance and significant positive SCA effects observed in crosses such as P₁×P₂ and P₃×P₄ highlight their potential as promising hybrids. These crosses involved high × low and low × low general combiners, demonstrating that high SCA effects can arise from diverse parental combinations.

The cross P₁×P₂ exhibited one of the highest significant positive SCA effects for grain yield and related traits, whereas some high × high general combiner crosses showed relatively lower SCA effects and mean performance. For days to maturity, crosses P₃×P₅ and P₃×P₆ showed significant negative SCA effects, indicating earliness, and involved low × low general combiners. Parents P₃, P₄, and P₅, which showed significant positive GCA effects for grain yield and negative GCA effects for days to tasseling, silking, and maturity, may be extensively utilized as donor parents in hybridization programs.

Among the hybrids, P₁×P₂ and P₁×P₅ exhibited significant and desirable SCA effects for days to tasseling and silking, number of grains per cob, and grain yield per plant, and were identified as the best specific combiners for these traits. These were followed by crosses P₃×P₅ and P₃×P₆, which showed favorable SCA effects for days to silking and maturity along with several yield components. The most promising crosses for improving grain number and grain yield were P₁×P₂ and P₅×P₆, as they exhibited the highest significant positive SCA effects for these traits. Additionally, crosses P₄×P₅ and P₅×P₆ also showed good performance for grain yield and involved low × average general combiners.

Parents with desirable GCA effects for grain yield (P₄), reduced grain number per cob (P₁), and early maturity (P₄) may be effectively used as donor parents in hybrid breeding programs. Overall, the superior crosses P₁×P₂, P₄×P₅, and P₅×P₆ showed excellent potential and can be utilized for the development of high-yielding maize hybrids and for the exploitation of heterosis.

Table 1. ANOVA (MS value) for combining ability of seven characters of maize inbreds in a 6;6 diallel cross

Sources of variation	df	DT	DS	DM	NRC	NGR	NGC	GYP
Inbreds	24	7.348**	5.938**	77.896**	5.463*	9.395**	947.161**	68.778**
GCA	5	15.009**	10.473**	180.405**	1.433*	94.069**	12916.598**	1035.173**
SCA	15	4.795**	4.427**	45.030**	2.581**	12.116**	3571.143**	286.216**
Crosses	20	7.348**	5.938**	77.789**	1.544*	32.604**	5907.507**	473.455**
Error	40	4.236	3.242	5.0989	3.489	17.689	3376.707	270.629
GCA/SCA		3.159	2.365	4.414	0.745	7.764	3.6169	3.6167
F value		**	**	***	**	***	***	***

*, ** indicate significant at p=0.05 and p= 0.01, respectively.

Table 2. Estimation of GCA of parents for different characters in maize inbreds

Parent s	DT		DS		DM		NRC		NKR		NKC		GYP	
	Mea n	gca	Mea n	gca	Mean	gca	Mean	gca	Mean	gca	Mean	gca	Mean	gca
P ₁	91.00	1.422	93.00	1.265	145.30	-4.448**	12.134	0.388	14.650	0.237	68.750	18.422**	65.575	-8.301**
P ₂	90.75	-0.743	97.75	-0.134	152.90	2.659**	11.865	0.132	13.530	-0.846	66.240	7.419*	79.535	-7.018**
P ₃	92.06	-0.428	95.06	-0.267	148.25	2.975**	11.685	0.173	14.500	1.045	69.240	19.055**	78.540	0.358
P ₄	90.70	-3.547*	90.70	-2.487*	150.60	-5.402**	11.330	-0.198	15.350	-1.071	66.855	-15.88*	82.900	3.178**

P ₅	89.5 0	0.452	92.5 0	0.114	149.9 0	-0.576	10.75 0	- 0.252	14.75 0	0.789	65.90 0	2.703* *	81.95 0	8.877 **
P ₆	91.2 0	- 0.155	93.9 0	- 0.491	149.9 5	0.793	12.35 0	- 0.242	14.35 0	0.311	65.35 0	- 2.880* *	75.12 0	2.906 **
SE (gi)	0.34 5		0.33 5		0.420		0.130		0.783		10.82 8		3.065	
LSD, 5%	1.53 2		1.83 1		15.27 9		1.112		1.843		1.749		1.749	

Table 3. Estimation of SCA of crosses for different characters in maize inbreds

Crosse s	DT		DS		DM		NR C		NKR		NKC		GY P	
	Mea n	sca	Mea n	sca	Mea n	sca	Mea n	sca	Mea n	sca	Mean	sca	Mea n	sca
P ₁ × P ₂	97.8 40	0.05 4	100. 110	4.757* *	146. 223	2.244* *	14.6 66	7.61* *	28.7 80	3.034* *	383.6 70	56.096 **	108. 617	15.880 **
P ₁ × P ₃	97.2 80	- 0.31 3	98.8 90	0.671	149. 473	3.178* *	14.3 86	0.253	31.0 00	-1.253	342.5 03	- 11.127* *	96.9 62	- 3.150* *
P ₁ × P ₄	95.3 56	- 0.56 9	98.6 13	0.614	142. 110	0.192	13.7 76	2.248 *	28.1 66	-0.324	366.8 43	3.251* *	103. 853	0.920
P ₁ × P ₅	96.5 56	0.95 8	99.9 43	- 2.343* *	144. 473	-0.270	13.7 23	3.398 *	27.3 60	4.124* *	400.0 20	16.295 **	113. 245	4.613* *
P ₁ × P ₆	94.7 50	1.03 5	97.6 10	-0.384	151. 276	7.163* *	12.7 12	- 4.80* *	24.5 83	1.300	356.8 86	- 5.745* *	101. 034	-1.626
P ₂ × P ₃	93.6 10	0.07 8	97.9 73	2.153* *	156. 723	3.319* *	13.6 10	- 2.80* *	27.5 83	-0.058	351.8 03	- 6.360* *	99.5 95	-1.800
P ₂ × P ₄	94.9 43	- 0.00 8	97.5 26	0.927	152. 416	1.391	13.2 20	- 0.457	24.1 40	- 3.58**	335.6 10	- 32.514 **	95.0 11	- 9.205* *
P ₂ × P ₅	94.2 23	- 0.23 0	96.9 46	-0.254	150. 833	0.981	12.4 70	- 0.617	28.5 56	- 4.30**	316.3 26	- 71.930 **	89.5 51	20.363 **
P ₂ × P ₆	93.4 73	0.94 6	95.9 16	-0.678	148. 526	- 2.694* *	13.0 01	0.093	27.8 90	-1.121	353.6 20	- 13.545 **	100. 109	3.834* *
P ₃ × P ₄	93.1 40	- 0.56 9	94.9 46	- 3.519* *	143. 803	3.185* *	13.0 26	- 0.480	29.6 10	-1.101	367.3 87	- 26.795 **	- 15.3 60	- 7.585* *
P ₃ × P ₅	95.4 43	0.95 8	97.7 7	0.708	146. 723	- 6.364* *	12.8 86	- 5.04* *	28.8 31	-1.635	390.9 03	- 23.411* *	110. 664	- 6.627* *
P ₃ × P ₆	95.1 36	1.03 5	97.8 90	- 3.427* *	144. 750	- 4.813* *	12.7 76	- 5.247 *	29.7 23	- 2.40**	367.6 80	- 25.542 **	104. 089	- 7.231* *
P ₄ × P ₅	94.4 43	0.07 8	96.6 93	- 3.154* *	149. 890	-1.039	13.2 50	0.231	24.5 56	3.126* *	448.8 83	24.238 **	126. 973	6.861* *

F M Ali Haydar, et al, Estimation of Combining Ability of Maize Inbreds

P ₄ × P ₆	93.9 73	- 0.00 8	95.6 66	-0.154	147. 125	1.730	12.6 40	0.208	30.2 90	4.253* *	410.8 83	7.699* *	116. 321	2.181* *
P ₅ × P ₆	94.5 26	- 0.23 0	96.6 96	2.146* *	148. 176	0.191	13.2 23	0.451	31.1 93	2.801* *	449.1 37	25.821 **	127. 150	7.309* *
SE (gi)	0.94 6		0.92 1		1.15 5		0.35 7		2.15 2		29.73 8		8.41 8	
LSD (5%)	ns		ns		*		ns		**		***		***	

CONCLUSION

Parents exhibiting significant positive general combining ability (GCA) for grain yield (P₁ and P₄), negative GCA effects for days to silking and maturity (P₁ and P₃), and lower grain number (P₅) may be effectively utilized as donor parents in hybridization programs. The four superior crosses, namely P₁ × P₂, P₁ × P₅, P₃ × P₅, and P₃ × P₆, demonstrated promising performance and can be exploited for the development of high-yielding maize hybrids as well as for the utilization of hybrid vigor. These crosses should be further evaluated through multi-location and advanced-generation trials to confirm their stability and yield potential.

REFERENCES

1. Abdel-Moneam, M.A., A.N. Attia, M.I. El-Emery and E.A. Fayed. 2009. Combining ability and heterosis for some agronomic traits in crosses of maize. *Pakistan J. Biolo.Sci.* 12(5): 433-438.
2. Ahmad. S.Q., S. Khan, M. Ghaffar and P. Ahmad. 2011. Genetic diversity analysis for yield and other parameters in maize (*Zea mays* L.) genotype. *Asian J. Agril. Sci.* 3(5): 385-388.
3. Ahmed, S., F. Khatun, M.S. Uddin, B.R. Banik and N. A. Ivy. 2008. Combining ability and heterosis in maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Bangladesh J. Pl. Breed.Genet.* 21(2): 27-32.
4. Alam, A.K.M.M., S. Ahmed, M. Begum and M.K. Sultan. 2008. Heterosis and combining ability for grain yield and its contributing characters in maize. *Bangladesh J. Agril. Res.* 33 (3): 375-379.
5. Amiruzzaman, M. 2010. Exploitation of hybrid vigour from normal and quality protein maize crosses. Ph.D Dissertation, Dept. Genetics and Plant Breeding, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh, P. 200.
6. Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS). Statistical year book of Bangladesh. Statistic Division, Ministry of Planning, Dhaka, Bangladesh. 2016. P. 92.
7. Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS). Statistical year book of Bangladesh. Statistic Division, Ministry of Planning, Dhaka, Bangladesh. 2016. P. 92.
8. Falconer, D.S. 1981. Introduction of quantitative genetics. *Agric. Res. Coun. Unit Amin.Genet., Univ., Edinburg.* P.92.
9. Griffing, B. 1956. Concept of general and specific combining ability in relation to diallel crossing systems. *Aust. J. Biol. Sci.* 9: 463-493.
10. Griffings, B. 1956. Concept of general and specific combining in relation of diallel crossing systems. *Aus. J. Bio. Sci.* 9:463-93.
11. Gurung, D.B., M.L.C. George and Q.D. Delacruz. 2008. Heterosis and combining ability of Nepalese Yellow maize Populations. Book of Abstracts. The 10 th Asian Reg. Maize Workshop. October 20-23, Makassar, Indonesia. P. 88.
12. Halluer, A.R. and J.B. Miranda. 1981. Quantitative genetics in maize breeding. Iowa State Univ. Press, Ames, USA.
13. Haluauer, A.R. 1990. Germplasm sources and breeding strategies for line development in the 1990's. *Annu. Corn Sorghum Res. Proc.* 45: 64-79.
14. Ivy, N.A. and M.S. Howlader. 2000. Combining ability in maize. *Bangladesh J. Agril. Res.* 25: 385-392. Kadir, M.M. 2010. Development of quality protein maize hybrids and their adaptation in Bangladesh. PhD Dissertation, Dept. Genetics & Plant Breeding, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh.
15. Mather, K. and J.L. Jinks. 1971. *Biometrical Genetics*. Second Edition. Chapman and Hall Ltd. London.
16. N. M. S. K ARIM, S. AHMED, A. H. AKHI, M. Z. A. T ALUKDER and A. KARIM. 2018. Combining Ability and Heterosis Study in Maize Inbreds throughout Diallel Mating Design. *Bangladesh J. Agril. Res.* 43(4): 599-609. ISSN: 0258-7122 (Print), 2408-8293 (Online).
17. Singh, R.K. Chaudhry, B.D. *Biometrical Methods in Quantitative Genetic Analysis*. Kalyani Publishers, Ludhiana, New Dehli, India. p. 303. (1979).
18. Wilson, N.D., D.E. Eeibel and McNew. 1078. Diallel analysis of grain yield, percent protein in grain sorghum. *Crop Sci.* 18: 491-494.
19. Yan, W. and K. Manjit. 2003. GGE Biplot Analysis. Pp.207-228.